

A Bernoulli pseudo-spectral method for solving nonlinear fractional integro-differential equations

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Abstract

In this paper, a Bernoulli pseudo-spectral method for solving nonlinear Volterra integro-differential equations of fractional order is considered. The fractional derivative is described in the Caputo sense. The suggested technique transform these types of equations to the solution of a system of algebraic equations. The technique is applied to some problems to show the validity and applicability of the proposed method.

Keywords: Fractional calculus, Caputo derivative, Bernoulli polynomials, Volterra integro-differential equations.

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1 Introduction

Fractional differential equations (FDEs) are generalizations of ordinary differential equations to an arbitrary order. A history of the development of fractional differential operators can be found in [1].

Definition 1.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as [2]

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral we have [2]:

$$I^\nu t^\beta = \frac{\Gamma(\beta + 1)}{\Gamma(\beta + \nu + 1)} t^{\nu+\beta}, \quad \beta > -1. \quad (2)$$

Definition 1.2. Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as [2]

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n - 1 < \nu \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}, t > 0. \quad (3)$$

For the Caputo derivative we have the following two basic properties[2]:

$$(i) D^\nu I^\nu f(t) = f(t), \quad (ii) I^\nu D^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

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Definition 1.3. Bernoulli polynomials of order m can be defined with the following formula [3]

$$B_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} B_{m-i} t^i. \quad (4)$$

Theorem 1.4. Let $D^\nu y(x)$ be approximated by the Bernoulli polynomials ($D^\nu y(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x)$), and also suppose $n - 1 < \nu \leq n$. Then

$$y(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} x^{r+\nu} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)}(0) \frac{x^i}{i!}, \quad (5)$$

where $b_{k,r} = \binom{k}{r} \frac{\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(r+1+\nu)} B_{k-r}$.

Proof. Applying operator I^ν , on both sides of $D^\nu y(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)}(0) \frac{x^i}{i!} &= I^\nu \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x) \right) = I^\nu \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k \sum_{r=0}^k \binom{k}{r} B_{k-r} x^r \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k \binom{k}{r} B_{k-r} I^\nu(x^r) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k \binom{k}{r} B_{k-r} \frac{\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(r+1+\nu)} x^{r+\nu} = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} x^{r+\nu}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 1.5. In this paper, we consider the following equation

$$D^\nu y(x) - \lambda \int_0^x k(x,t) F(y(t)) dt = f(x), \quad 0 \leq x < 1, n - 1 < \nu \leq n, \quad (6)$$

$$y^{(i)}(0) = \delta_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1, n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (7)$$

Solution. We approximate $D^\nu y(x)$ as:

$$D^\nu y(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x). \quad (8)$$

From Eqs. (6), (7), (8) and Theorem 1, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x) - \lambda \int_0^x k(x,t) F \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} t^{r+\nu} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)} \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) dt = f(x). \quad (9)$$

Now, we collocate (9) at the zeros $x_p, p = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$ of Legendre polynomial $P_m(t)$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x_p) - \lambda \int_0^{x_p} k(x_p,t) F \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} t^{r+\nu} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)} \frac{t^i}{i!} \right) dt = f(x_p). \quad (10)$$

Then, we transfer the t -interval $[0, x_p]$ into τ -interval $[-1, 1]$ by change of variable $\tau = \frac{2}{x_p}t - 1$,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x_p) - \lambda \frac{x_p}{2} \int_{-1}^1 k(x_p, \frac{x_p}{2}(\tau+1)) F(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} (\frac{x_p}{2}(\tau+1))^{r+\nu} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)} \frac{(\frac{x_p}{2}(\tau+1))^i}{i!}) d\tau = f(x_p). \quad (11)$$

By using the Gauss-Legendre integration formula [4], for $p = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$, we have:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} c_k B_k(x_p) - \lambda \frac{x_p}{2} \sum_{q=1}^m \omega_q k(x_p, \frac{x_p}{2}(\tau_q+1)) F(\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \sum_{r=0}^k c_k b_{k,r} (\frac{x_p}{2}(\tau_q+1))^{r+\nu} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y^{(i)} \frac{(\frac{x_p}{2}(\tau_q+1))^i}{i!}) = f(x_p), \quad (12)$$

where τ_q , $q = 1, 2, \dots, m$, are zeros of Legendre polynomial $p_m(x)$ and $\omega_j = \frac{-2}{(n+1)p'_m(x_j)p_{m+1}(x_j)}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Eq. (12), give m nonlinear algebraic equations which can be solved, for the unknowns c_k , $k = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$, using Newton's iterative method. Finally, $y(x)$ given in (5) can be calculated.

2 Main results

First, we consider the following equation [5]

$$D^\nu y(x) - \int_0^x [y(t)]^3 dt = e^x - \frac{1}{3}e^{3x} + \frac{1}{3}, \quad 0 \leq x < 1, 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (13)$$

subject to the initial condition $y(0) = 1$. The exact solution of this problem, when $\nu = 1$, is $y(x) = e^x$. Table 1 shows the approximate solutions obtained for different values of t by using the present method for $m = 4, 6, 8$ and $\nu = 1$, the second Chebyshev wavelet method [5] for $k = 5, M = 2$ and $\nu = 1$, together with the exact solutions. Also, the numerical results for $y(x)$ with $m = 8$ and $\nu = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1$ are plotted in Fig. 1.

Table 1: Comparison of numerical solutions with the other methods for $\nu = 1$

t	Exact solution	Present method			Ref[5]
		$m = 4$	$m = 6$	$m = 8$	
0	1	1	1	1	1.000122
0.2	1.221403	1.220677	1.221408	1.221403	1.221645
0.4	1.491825	1.490795	1.491828	1.491825	1.492295
0.6	1.822119	1.821352	1.822117	1.822119	1.823061
0.8	2.225541	2.224992	2.225543	2.225541	2.227565

Then, consider the following equation [5]

$$D^\nu y(x) - \int_0^x [y(t)]^2 dt = -1, \quad 0 \leq x < 1, 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (14)$$

subject to the initial condition $y(0) = 0$. Table 2, shows the numerical for $\nu = 0.8, 0.9, 1$, by using the present method, when $m = 8$, and the second Chebyshev wavelet method [5], for $k = 6, M = 2$.

Figure 1: Comparison of $y(x)$ for $m = 8$, with $\nu = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1$ and exact solution

Table 2: The numerical results for various values of ν

t	Exact solution	Present method			Ref[5]		
		$\nu = 1$	$\nu = 0.9$	$\nu = 0.8$	$\nu = 1$	$\nu = 0.9$	$\nu = 0.8$
0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.00017	-0.00055
0.1250	-0.12498	-0.12498	-0.15997	-0.20339	-0.12498	-0.16003	-0.20344
0.2500	-0.24968	-0.24968	-0.29791	-0.35281	-0.24968	-0.29794	-0.35281
0.3750	-0.37336	-0.37336	-0.42702	-0.48422	-0.37336	-0.42702	-0.48420
0.5000	-0.49482	-0.49482	-0.54829	-0.60159	-0.49483	-0.54828	-0.60156
0.6250	-0.61243	-0.61243	-0.66089	-0.70527	-0.61245	-0.66090	-0.70527
0.7500	-0.72415	-0.72415	-0.76327	-0.79452	-0.72418	-0.76332	-0.79457
0.8750	-0.82767	-0.82767	-0.85360	-0.86834	-0.82770	-0.85365	-0.86838

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